
Influence of Social Media on Grade 12 HUMSS Students' Academic Behavior

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the possible influences of social media to the students' academic behavior. Awareness of the potential outcomes of using social media can help them understand the possible impacts. The goal of this study is to develop plans to enhance students' holistic development and encourage responsible social media use by addressing these consequences. This research will be conducted at a Senior High School in Digos City. The sampling design for this study is a survey questionnaire. Furthermore, the study's respondents are Grade 12 HUMSS students who use various social media platforms. To add to that, this study will use the survey instrument, specifically the questionnaire. This study will use an attitudinal measure, a quantitative way to assess a person's attitude. This study aims to collect data and information regarding students' academic behavior. The findings conclude that social media helps the students' in various ways, including the improvements they made by searching for the things they wanted to understand. However, social media also distracted the students, affecting their study habits and academic performance. In conclusion, social media affected the students' lives moderately. They are distracted by social media, but their academic behavior is untroubled at all.

KEYWORDS: Social Media, Addiction, Academic Behavior, Positive and Negative Influence, Students, Social Networks, HUMSS, Grade 12

1. INTRODUCTION

Social media and social networks significantly impact the student community, and such technology is progressively permeating everyone's daily lives (Abbas et al., 2019). Students use social media to connect virtually with others, including family, friends, peers, teachers, members of interest groups, and even strangers (Junco, 2014; Muñoz-Carril et al., 2018; West et al., 2024). Moreover, existing literature views social media as a catalyst and enabler of innovation (Bhimani et al., 2019). They enable individuals to share ideas, information, and thoughts through online groups and networks (Carr & Hayes, 2015).

Recent statistics published by Petrosyan (2024) show that as of April 2024, there were 5.44 billion internet users worldwide. Of this total, 62.6 percent were social media users. Martin et al. (2018) surveyed 593 middle school students about digital footprints and concerns about social media. Results found that these students use social media most often to connect with their friends, share pictures, and discover what others are doing. However, a study conducted by (Mim et al., 2018) in Tangail, Bangladesh, found that many respondents reported negative consequences such as late assignment submission, decreased study time, and poor academic performance due to excessive social media use. Some students also reported positive feedback regarding their involvement in social issues through social media, though harmful activities such as involvement in militant activities were also noted.

In the Philippines, social media use has become widespread and practically unavoidable, altering how students engage, connect, and socialize; it has become an intrinsic part of their social and cultural landscape. As a result, students dedicate a significant amount of time to social media (Tus et al., 2021).

Given past research findings on the effects of social media, the nature of social media's impact on youth in Davao City has both positive and negative implications. While social media allows for contact, information sharing, and self-expression, it also poses threats to mental health and well-being, mainly when used excessively or recklessly. To address these problems, interventions are required to increase digital literacy, appropriate social media use, and mental health awareness among Davao City adolescents (Grenien & Campos, 2023).

However, previous research has not detailed the possible impacts of social media influence on students' academic behavior. This gap in research encourages further study to help students, especially Grade 12 HUMSS students. As researchers, it is crucial to investigate this issue because students need to understand how social media affects their academic behavior. Awareness of the potential outcomes of using social media can help them understand possible impacts.

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This study is anchored on Social Learning Theory. According to the social learning theory, people pick up new skills by watching, copying, and modeling the conduct of others, especially in social situations. Regarding social media and academic behavior, students could look up to and copy their friends' or other influential users' study techniques and conduct.

The study focuses on the influence of social media on the academic performance of Senior High School Grade 12 HUMSS students. It explores the following aspects: student addiction to social networks, students' exposure to social media, and their use of social media.

The study on the influence of social media on students' academic behavior is crucial because it helps us understand how platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok affect things like study habits, attention span, and grades. By examining this, educators can develop strategies to support students in balancing their online and offline lives for better academic success.

This study examines how social media influences the academic performance of Grade 12 HUMSS students. The goal is to develop plans to enhance students' holistic development and encourage responsible social media use by addressing these consequences. Specifically, this study aims to determine the influence of social media on students' academic behavior. It sought answers from the following: (1) to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of gender and age; (2) to assess the level of influence of social media on the students in terms of students' addiction to social networks, exposure of students to social media, and use of social media; and (3) to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of the influence of social media on academic behavior when respondents are grouped by profile.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Research Respondents

This research was conducted at a Senior High School in Digos City. The respondents for this study consist of Grade 12 students enrolled in the School Year (SY) 2023-2024 which come from Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand. The study used a simple random sampling technique. This sampling technique is a method which has an inclusive and equitable representation of drawing samples from the general population (Gupta & Shabbir, 2008 as cited in Diquito et al., 2024). Based on the characteristics of the population, the study will comprise 93 respondents in total, which is a representative sample size. Other strands and Grade 11 students are excluded from the study.

2.2 Research Instruments

The research instrument utilized in the study is a structured survey questionnaire designed to measure various aspects of social media usage and its impact on student's academic performance and behavior. The following are the indicators: student addiction to social networks, students' exposure to social media, and the students' use of social media.

In assessing the influence of social media on the academic performance of Grade 12 HUMSS Students, the five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions were used as follows:

Table 1: Range of Means and Interpretation

Range of Means	Numerical Value	Verbal Description	Descriptive Meaning
4.51 – 5.00	5	Very High	This means that the level of influence of social media is always manifested.
3.51 – 4.50	4	High	This means that the level of influence of social media is often manifested.
2.51 – 3.00	3	Moderate	This means that the level of influence of social media is sometimes manifested.
1.51 – 2.50	2	Low	This means that the level of influence of social media is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.50	1	Very Low	This means that the level of influence of social media is not manifested at all.

2.3 Research Design and Procedure

The study employed a quantitative research design using a survey method to gather data. Descriptive research design describes conditions between variables (Calmorin & Calmorin, 2007; Creswell, 2013). A structured questionnaire with Likert-scale items is utilized to assess various indicators of social media usage and its impact on academic performance.

To obtain data, the researchers formally followed the initial steps. Permission from school authorities was granted. Upon the approval of the request, the researchers administered the survey questionnaire to the selected students via the Google Form link during regular school hours. Instructions were given to ensure accurate responses.

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The obtained data were coded and entered into statistical software. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize demographic data. The means and standard deviations were calculated for each item to determine social media's influence level. Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare differences in social media influence based on gender and Age. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table 2 shows the demographic profile of Grade 12 HUMSS respondents. In terms of sex, female respondents consist of the majority of the respondents ($f=55$, $\%=59.1$) compared to male respondents ($f=38$, $\%=40.9$). While, in terms of age, majority of respondents were 16-18 years old ($f=69$, $\%=74.2$) and followed by 19 to 21 years old ($f= 24$, $\%=25.8$).

Table 2: Demographic Profile of Respondents (n= 93)

Profile	f	%
Sex		
Male	38	40.9
Female	55	59.1
Age		
16-18 y.o.	69	74.2
19-21 y.o.	24	25.8

3.2 Level of Influence of Social Media on Academic Performance of Grade 12 HUMSS Students

Table 3 presents the influence of social media on the academic performance of Grade 12 HUMSS students in terms of students' addiction to social networks, students' exposure to social media, and use of social media. The overall mean score obtained is 2.92, which is described as moderate. This means that the level of influence social media has on Grade 12 HUMSS students is sometimes manifested. The mean score obtained for each indicator is presented and discussed below.

3.2.1 Student addiction to social network

Table 3 shows the level of influence of social media on academic performance of Grade 12 HUMSS students in terms of addiction to social networks. It shows that the overall mean of this variable is 3.02, which is described as moderate. Data implies that the respondents sometimes manifest addiction to social networks. It suggests that the respondents are aware of the impact of social networks on their academic performance but may have mixed feelings about the seriousness of the issue. Respondents generally agree that social network distracts them from their studies. Also, they generally agree that their grade have not improved since engaging in social network activities, though the spread of responses is wider.

Table 3. Level of Influence of Social Media on Grade 12 HUMSS Students' Academic Performance

Indicators	Mean	SD
Student addiction to social networks	3.02	0.99
Students' exposure to social media	2.80	1.12
Use of social media	2.93	0.99

This result agrees with the statement of Griffiths and Kuss (2017), who assert that social media addiction is an excessive concern with and usage of social media platforms, which has detrimental implications in many areas of life. Parents must monitor their children to minimize using their gadgets, and students must also know their limits when using social media. Instead of playing, use social media for activities in school like research, assignments, and the like. This will help students improve their academic success and also not be prone to addiction.

3.2.2 Students' exposure to social media and academic performance

Table 3 shows the level of influence of social media on academic performance of Grade 12 HUMSS students in terms of students' exposure level to social media networks. It shows that the overall mean of this variable is 2.80, which is described as moderate. This suggests that respondents have mixed opinions on the impact of social media exposure on their academic performance. The data indicates that respondents' experiences and perceptions are pretty varied, as there is no clear tendency toward positive or negative impacts. Some respondents feel negatively affected by unlimited access to Facebook, but the opinion is not strong. Although some respondents believe that Twitter helps their academic performance, however, other respondents do not see any improvement at all.

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Students, exposure to social media networks does not uniformly influence the respondents' academic performance. While some students believe that academic discussions on social media are beneficial, others do not see any significant impact. The variability in responses suggests that the impact of social media on academic performance is subjective and likely influenced by personal usage habits and preferences.

This result agrees with the statement of Junco et al., (2011), who investigated the frequency and duration of social media use among college students and found that heavy users tended to have lower academic performance than moderate or light users. Similarly, Yotyodying et al. (2022) explored the types of activities students engage in on social media platforms and their associations with academic outcomes.

3.2.3 Use of social media and student academic performance

Table 3 shows the level of influence of social media on academic performance of Grade 12 HUMSS students in terms of the use of social media. It shows that the overall mean of this variable is 2.93, which is described as moderate. The data indicates that respondents see social media as a valuable tool for improving their learning experiences and as a part of their academic activities. However, some social media activities, like engaging in academic forums on Facebook, might impair their understanding. The diverse perspectives on most items indicate that respondents' individual experiences with social media vary significantly. Respondents generally agree more strongly that social media can effectively enhance their academic learning experience. Also, respondents disagree that their academic performance would not improve even if they stopped using social media.

This result agrees with the statement of Rideout and Fox (2018), who investigated the frequency and duration of social media use among adolescents and found that a significant portion of their daily screen time was dedicated to social networking platforms. Similarly, Chang et al. (2019) explored the types of activities students engage in on social media and their associations with academic outcomes.

3.3 Significant Difference in the Influence of Social Media on Grade 12 HUMSS Students' Academic Performance when grouped according to Sex

Table 4 shows the result of the Mann-Whitney U test comparing the perception of the influence of social media on academic behavior among the respondents when grouped according to sex. Mann-Whitney U test is a non-parametric test used when the assumptions of the t-test are not met. This test is appropriate for comparing perceptions between two groups when the data does not follow a normal distribution. The Mann-Whitney U test assesses whether there is a significant difference between the groups' perceptions. It can be observed that all indicators have p-values greater than 0.05, which means that we fail to reject the null hypothesis. This indicates no significant differences in students' activeness, exposure to social media, or use of social media when the respondents are grouped according to their sex.

This suggests that there is no significant difference in the perception of the influence of social media on academic behavior between male and female respondents. The results imply that both male and female respondents view the influence of social media on academic behavior similarly. There is no need for gender-specific approaches based on this aspect. The result generally suggests that sex does not play a role in shaping perceptions of social media's impact on academic aspects. This can be helpful information for educators, policymakers, and researchers interested in understanding and mitigating the effects of social media on student performance.

Table 4. Significant Difference in the Influence of Social Media on Grade 12 HUMSS Students' Academic Performance when grouped according to Sex

Indicators	Statistics	p
Student addiction to social networks	0.484	.629
Students' exposure to social media	1032	.919
Use of social media	1040	.972

The result agrees with the statement of Muscanell and Guadagno (2012), indicating that while social media use patterns may differ by gender, the impact on academic performance and behavior is not significantly different between genders. Studies have shown that male and female students engage with social media in ways that influence their academic behaviors, similarly, implying that gender-specific approaches are unnecessary in this context (Nketiah-Amponsah et al., 2017; Papastergiou & Solomonidou, 2005).

3.4 Significant Difference in the Influence of Social Media on Grade 12 HUMSS Students' Academic Performance when grouped according to Age

Table 5 shows the results of the Mann-Whitney U test, which compares respondents' opinions about the impact of social media on academic behavior based on their age group. Mann-Whitney U test is a non-parametric test used when the assumptions of the t-test

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are not met. This test is appropriate for comparing perceptions between two groups when the data does follow a normal distribution. The Mann-Whitney U test assesses whether there is a significant difference between the groups' perceptions. For each of the three indicators, student addictiveness, exposure of students to social media, and usage of social media, the mean and standard deviation values are given. The first two variables, Students' Addiction to Social Networks and Students' Exposure to Social Media, have p-values greater than 0.05, indicating no significant differences when grouped according to Age. However, the third variable, the use of social media, has a p-value close to 0.05, indicating a marginally significant difference. This suggests that the use of social media may have a slight impact on academic performance, but it is not strong enough to be considered statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Hence, exploring how specific types of social media use affect academic performance might be beneficial.

Table 5. Significant Difference in the Influence of Social Media on Grade 12 HUMSS Students' Academic Performance when grouped according to Age

Indicators	Statistics	p
Student addiction to social networks	0.345	.731
Students' exposure to social media	736	.419
Use of social media	1.930	.057

The result is supported by Chandrasiri and Samarasinghe (2021), suggesting that while addiction to social media and general exposure do not consistently result in significant academic performance changes, usage patterns play a nuanced role. The type and intensity of social media use, such as collaborative versus leisure activities may yield marginally significant impacts on performance academically.

4. CONCLUSION

The study on the influence of social media on the academic performance of Grade 12 HUMSS students provides a comprehensive understanding of the impact of social media usage. The findings indicate that social media affects students' academic behavior positively and negatively. Firstly, the study reveals that students manifested a high level of addiction to social networks, which often distracts them from their studies. This aligns with previous research indicating that excessive social media use can lead to decreased study time and poor academic performance. However, it is essential to note that the impact varies among students, highlighting the subjective nature of social media's influence. Secondly, students' exposure to social media influenced their academic performance moderately. While some students benefit from academic discussions on platforms like Twitter, others do not see significant improvements. This variability suggests that personal usage habits and preferences play a crucial role in determining the impact of social media on academic outcomes. Lastly, the study shows that students use social media to enhance their learning experiences. However, the overall effect is moderate, with concerns about potential impairments due to social media activities. The findings highlight the need for students to balance their online and offline lives to optimize academic success.

5. RECOMMENDATION

Social media offers chances to improve academically, but some risks should also be considered. Educators and parents should emphasize the importance of digital literacy and responsible social media use. By fostering awareness and providing guidance, students can better navigate social media challenges, ultimately supporting their academic and personal development. This study underlines the critical need for continued research and intervention to lessen the adverse effects of social media in educational contexts while maximizing its benefits.

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